

ANODIC OXIDATION OF FORMATE ION

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A study of the electrolysis of sodium formate in neutral solutions has been made, with particular reference to reactions at the anode. Current-anode potential curves are quite smooth and continuous. No abrupt changes or breaks are observed right up to high current densities.

In *M*-sodium formate solutions (a) carbon dioxide is the sole product up to a current density of 12.5 milliamperes per sq. cm., (b) between current densities 12.5 and 50 milliamps. small percentages of oxygen are also formed; (c) at and above a current density of 50 milliamps. small quantities of carbon monoxide and hydrogen are also among the products.

The formation of the different anode products has been explained on the basis of the formation of an unstable dimer of the formate radical and its subsequent catalytic decomposition on the platinum surface at different centres.

Anodic oxidation of formate ion has been the subject of numerous investigations. Earlier workers (Peterson, *Bull. Acad. Roy. Denmark*, 1897, 397; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, 33, 106; Salzer, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1902, 8, 893) found that in aqueous solutions, the main product at the anode was carbon dioxide at moderate concentrations, while in dilute solutions a certain amount of oxygen was also liberated. The ratio CO_2/O_2 was found to depend upon the dilution and the current density. Among the more recent investigations, those of E. Muller (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1923, 29, 264; 1927, 33, 561) and F. Muller (*ibid.*, 1927, 33, 173) are of particular interest and importance as they aimed at arriving at a mechanism for the anode reactions.* Both these investigators found the reaction to proceed quantitatively in accordance with the equation

From this significant relationship, the anodic reaction, resulting in the liberation of one molecule of carbon dioxide per two units of electricity, was accounted for by F. Muller by the expression

It is reasonable to infer that this overall anodic reaction takes place by the liberation of formate radicals on the anode in the first instance, followed by

In all the investigations referred to above, the electrolytes consisted of mixtures of formic acid or alkali formates either with sulphuric acid or alkalis. The liberation of carbon dioxide in pure alkali formate solutions is in all probability due to the reaction between freshly formed formate radicals at the anode. If free sulphuric acid or alkali happen to be present in the electrolyte, it is not improbable that the oxidation of the formate radical may, in part at least, be due to the liberation of oxygen atoms on a neutral anode surface due to secondary processes following the primary discharge of sulphate or hydroxyl ions. The occurrence of oxygen in anodic gases

in these mixed electrolytes may likewise, in part, be due to the same cause. These arguments do not, however, rule out the possibility of the formate radical itself, depending upon the circumstances prevailing on and around the surface of the anode, liberating oxygen by reacting with water in the following ways :

although the latter process would be less probable than the former. It was our object in the present investigation to obtain more information regarding the anodic reactions in the electrolysis of formates. We have carried out experiments using neutral formate solutions for electrolysis between polished platinum electrodes. Our results are somewhat different from those of previous workers in so far as we have found, rather surprisingly, carbon monoxide and even hydrogen among the anodic products at high current densities. These results and their interpretation form the subject matter of this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fig. 1. gives an idea of the experimental arrangement. The platinum electrodes A and B (each 2 cm. $\times$ 1 cm.) were covered by gas collecting contraptions of the shape indicated in the diagram. These, incidentally, helped to act as separators between the electrodes. The gas collectors were connected to gas burettes into which the gases were sucked for measurement and analysis at required intervals. A saturated KCl-calomel element was employed as the auxiliary for the measurement of anode potentials. Decomposition as well as anode potentials were all measured with a standard Leeds-Northrup potentiometer arrangement. The experiments were carried out with the electrolytic cell maintained at 30°. The gases collected were analysed by the usual methods of absorption.

Tables I, II and III give the potentiometric readings for the anode and polarisation potentials in *N*-formic acid, *N*-sodium formate and *N*/10-sodium formate respectively.

TABLE I

N-Formic acid.

Current.	Potential between electrodes.		Anode potential (against saturated KCl-calomel element 0.242 volt).	
0.02 m. amp.	0.6624	1.2074	0.4946	0.9860
0.04	0.8153	1.3083	0.6084	1.2220
0.06	0.8598	1.8598	1.5189	1.3679
0.08	1.0423	1.5685	0.8330	1.3974
0.10	1.1461	1.5842	0.8830	1.4113
0.12	1.2242	1.6542	0.9203	1.4472
0.16	1.3381	1.6858	0.9841	1.4740
0.20	1.4999	1.7282	1.0877	1.4963
0.30	1.7828	1.7916	1.3094	1.5280
0.40	1.9182	1.8788	1.3822	1.5594
0.50	2.0142	2.1264	1.4092	1.5802
0.60	2.0790	2.2820	1.4412	1.5842
0.80	2.2094	2.3116	1.4854	1.5858
1.00	2.3244	2.3916	1.4990	1.5976
1.50	2.4424	2.5854	1.5586	1.6554
2.00	2.5482	2.6480	1.5782	1.6764
3.00	2.680	2.7476	1.6500	1.7120
5.00	2.8286	2.9010	1.7206	1.7608
10.00	3.1692	3.2290	1.8546	1.8772
15.00	3.4760	3.4880	1.9604	1.9540

TABLE II

N-Sodium formate.

Current.	Potential between electrodes.		Anode potential (against saturated KCl-calomel element 0.242 volt).	
0.02 m. amp.	0.6675	0.7728	0.4985	0.5390
0.04	0.8985	0.9842	0.6250	0.7122
0.06	0.9742	1.0704	0.6824	0.8273
0.08	1.0272	1.1099	0.7001	0.8454
0.10	1.0630	1.1403	0.7126	0.8516
0.12	1.1129	1.1560	0.7278	0.8577
0.16	1.1836	1.1958	0.7425	0.8689
0.20	1.2534	1.2620	0.7536	0.8808
0.25	1.3685	1.3682	0.7616	0.8919
0.30	1.4440	1.4447	0.7742	0.8970
0.40	1.5492	1.5145	0.7852	0.9129
0.60	1.8682	1.8746	0.8162	0.9906
0.80	2.0200	2.2400	0.8498	1.0280
1.00	2.1058	2.3352	0.8614	1.0636
1.50	2.2340	2.5458	0.8968	1.1772
2.00	2.3612	2.6478	0.9452	1.2240
3.00	2.5592	2.7912	1.0832	1.2924
5.00	2.8164	2.9212	1.2122	1.3294
10.00	3.0844	3.0854	1.4164	1.4052
15.00	3.2140	3.1682	1.4688	1.5236
20.00	3.3370	3.3862	1.4540	1.5540

TABLE III

0.10N-Sodium formate.

Current.	Potential between electrodes.		Anode potential (against saturated KCl-calomel element 0.242 volt).	
0.02 m. amp.	0.6020	0.6820	0.4330	0.4480
0.04	0.8160	0.8820	0.6420	0.6810
0.06	0.8980	0.9874	0.7532	0.7948
0.08	0.9249	1.0246	0.7667	0.8088
0.10	0.9661	1.0545	0.7781	0.8184
0.12	0.9664	1.0594	0.7880	0.8293
0.16	0.9953	1.0860	0.8000	0.8438
0.20	1.0139	1.0590	0.8016	0.8592
0.25	1.0484	1.1761	0.8133	0.8846
0.30	1.0712	1.2175	0.8210	0.9248
0.40	1.1603	1.3784	0.8472	1.0256
0.50	1.2801	1.4372	0.8829	1.1117
0.60	1.4301	1.5435	0.9732	1.1557
1.00	1.9480	2.2320	1.0642	1.2004
1.50	2.3900	2.4780	1.1920	1.2614
2.00	2.5176	2.5570	1.2280	1.2870
3.00	2.6450	2.6836	1.2856	1.3322
5.00	2.8204	2.8644	1.3544	1.3660
8.00	3.032	3.0690	1.4540	1.4722

The current was in all cases gradually increased, starting from zero and the potentials recorded in columns 2 and 4 refer to the steady state reached at each current strength. Columns 3 and 5 indicate the potentials recorded while the current was gradually diminished, after going up to the highest current used, to the respective values. These potentials are higher than the ones observed when starting with fresh electrodes and the current gradually increased. The difference is obviously due to the change in the nature of the electrode surface when it has functioned for some time in electrolysis. These results and observations are reproducible even with the same set of electrodes when they are cleaned in the usual way and heated to redness and the experiments repeated.

Curves drawn from these figures indicate that the anode discharge potential is reached at very low current densities. The values are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Solution.	Anode discharge potential (corrected).	Decomposition potential.
N-Formic acid	0.897 volt	1.800 volt
N-Na formate	0.793	1.555
0.1N-Na formate	0.954	1.899

The curves in all cases are smooth and continuous and show no evidence of any sudden changes. Our results do not confirm the findings of E. Muller (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1927, 33, 561) who observed breaks and branches in the curves, working with formic acid-sulphuric acid mixtures and with a variety of electrode materials. So far as polished platinum electrodes are concerned, we feel justified in inferring that the primary anodic processes do not vary either considerably or suddenly at any stage. The variation of anode potential with increase in current density, after the discharge stage is reached, is great and is indicative of the formation of secondary products at the anode surface.

Anodic Products

The object of the next series of experiments was to see if there were any difference in the reactions and products at different current densities.

Previous workers, as stated above, have all noted that oxygen is one of the products in dilute solutions and at high current densities. We confined our experiments in this series mostly to *N*-sodium formate solutions. A few experiments have also been carried out at higher concentrations.

At higher as well as lower current densities, the evolution of gases at the anode was slow though continuous, in comparison with the rate of evolution of gas at the cathode. This, of course, is due to the partial absorption of the anodic carbon dioxide in water. With progress of electrolysis the rates tended to equalise. The quantity of hydrogen evolved at the cathode was always almost equal to the calculated amount on the basis of one molecule per two faradays of electricity. The volume of the cathodic gas could therefore be reckoned as a measure of the current passed and in all later experiments the silver coulometer was dispensed with.

In experiments with higher current densities, we maintained the neutrality of the electrolyte by adding small quantities of formic acid (calculated amounts) at intervals. At no stage of the experiments was the solution anything but very slightly acidic or alkaline. Tables V and VI illustrate the nature of the results of these experiments.

TABLE V

Electrolyte = *M*. Na formate.
Current = 100 m. amps.

Time. Start	Anode potential (corrected). 2.4674 volts	Volume of gas	
		Anode. 7.50 c.c.	Cathode. 52.50 c.c.
1 hr.	2.4778	16.50	107.00
2	2.5268	28.00	155.30
3	2.5556	43.00	210.00
4	2.5946		

TABLE VI

Electrolyte = *M*. Na formate.
Current = 1000 m. amps.
Anode potential = 5.742 to 5.7995 volts.

Time. 1st half hour	Vol. of gas per 10 minutes.	
	Anode. 41.0 c.c.	Cathode 89.10 c.c.
2nd	58.20	89.60
3rd	70.40	91.00
4th	80.50	92.10
5th	85.00	91.50
6th	90.00	91.00

It will be seen from these two tables that the rate of evolution of gas from the anode increases with time, and attains with progress of electrolysis the same value as the rate of evolution of cathodic hydrogen. The long interval involved in the attainment of the equality is understandable from the well known slow rate of dissolution of carbon dioxide in water and consequent delay in attaining the state of saturation.

Table VII gives the results of analysis of anodic gas evolved at different current densities. Figures in vertical columns 4 and 5 are intended to show the rate of evolution anode gases. At current densities of 50 milliamperes and above per sq. cm. a residue was found to be left after the absorption of carbon dioxide and oxygen. Careful analysis proved this to consist of carbon monoxide and hydrogen. In these runs of

experiments in which small volumes of these gases were found, the experiments were subjected to careful repetitions and a minimum of 100 c.c. of gas was collected and used for each analysis. The percentages shown in the table represent the mean of three experimental observations in each case.

TABLE VII

Current density (m. amp./cm ²).	Anode potential (volts)	Time taken to collect the gas	Volume of anode gas.	Percentage of			
				CO ₂ .	O ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ .
<i>M</i> -Sodium formate soln.							
1.25 a	1.4581—1.4988	12 hours	6.5 c.c.	100			
2.5	1.5104—1.5678	6	14.2	100			
6.25	1.6791—1.7628	4	32.0	100			
12.50	1.8908—1.9028	3	40.40	96	4.3		
25.00	2.4674—2.5580	1	27.9	91	9.0		
50.00	3.8382	1	48.20	87	6.5	3.3	3.0
250.00	5.742	(a) 10 minutes in 1st half hour	41.00	55	35	6.9	2.0
		(b) 10 min. in 2nd half hour	56.50	61	28	6.3	4.0
		(c) 10 min. in 3rd half hour	71.0	67	20	7.8	5.0
<i>2M</i> -Sodium formate soln.							
50				90	7	1.6	1.4
125				86	9.5	2.6	1.9
<i>4M</i> -Sodium formate soln.							
52				92.8	4.2	1.1	1.8
125				90.5	5.5	1.80	1.0
250				91.0	6.5	1.30	1.0
<i>M/10</i> -Sodium formate soln.							
250				28.4	69.7	1.8	—

DISCUSSION

The variation of anode potential with progress of electrolysis at the same current density is consistent with experience in all electrolytic phenomena due mainly to a change in the nature of the electrode surface caused by adsorption of electrode products, the nature and extent of which also vary with time, as well as the mechanical disintegration, particularly at higher current densities, and consequent variation of the electronic forces on the electrode surface. The evolution of oxygen commences at a current density near about 12.5 milliamp. per sq. cm. The potential at the anode (1.9 volts) at this current density is very much above the overvoltage of oxygen observed in neutral solutions of other salts (1.41 in neutral chlorate solutions at a current density of 100 milliamps. on smooth platinum; cf. Howard, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1923, 48, 51). There is no reason therefore to believe that the liberation of oxygen at any stage is the result of a primary anodic process. At still higher current densities (50 milliamps.

and above) the occurrence of carbon monoxide and hydrogen, even though in small quantities, points to a variety of secondary processes following the primary discharge of formate ion.

At low current densities, carbon dioxide is the only product and it is the predominant product at all current densities. We should therefore, particularly in view of the current efficiency of the process, regard the normal secondary reaction to be

At higher current densities the concentration of formate radicals would be much greater and the formation of oxygen might be catalytically favoured on a few spots in accordance with the equations

followed by

It should be noted that at the highest current density employed in our experiments there is an apparent diminution in the O_2/CO_2 ratio with the progress of electrolysis, apparent on account of the fact that in the earlier stages a good portion of the CO_2 actually formed is absorbed in water. But the increase in the quantities of carbon monoxide and hydrogen, on a percentage basis, with progress of electrolysis is real and has to be accounted for.

The formation of carbon monoxide at the anode is in all probability due to the platinum-catalysed reaction

This reaction should, of course, be occurring at centres other than the ones promoting reactions (1) and (2). It appears also reasonable to assume that the oxygen atoms formed in (2) have no access to the spots where CO is formed.

Reactions (1) and (3) are both indicated here as bimolecular with reference to the formate radical. Whether they react in this particular way on the surface of polished platinum or by the formation of an unstable dimer $(\text{HCOO})_2$, it is obvious that this complex, which may be regarded as an unstable isomer of oxalic acid, undergoes decomposition in the same ways as does oxalic acid under different conditions. Reaction (1) is similar to oxalic acid decomposition in glycerine and (3) is comparable to the dehydration decomposition of oxalic acid.

It is interesting to recall in this context, the observations of Emil Bauer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1928, 11, 372) who obtained small yields of carbon monoxide and oxygen at the anode in the electrolysis of *anhydrous formic acid*. Bauer explained all his results, including the formation of carbon dioxide and formic acid at the anode, on the basis of the formation of formyl peroxide and its subsequent decomposition. He formulated the following reactions :

He found ample evidence for the formation of formyl peroxide and even estimated it quantitatively.

In aqueous solutions, we tried in vain, to find any evidence for the formation of any such peroxide. It appears probable that in anhydrous formic acid (*i.e.* in the absence of water) the peroxide is readily formed at the anode and decomposes later. In aqueous solutions therefore we feel justified in explaining the formation of CO_2 , O_2 and CO by the mechanism of surface catalysis as in (1), (2) and (3).

The most interesting feature of our results is that hydrogen is one of the minor constituents of the anodic gases. It is interesting in so far as it comes out of the same electrode from the surface of which oxygen also escapes and in much larger quantities. This could happen under only one circumstance and that is when the centres of hydrogen formation happen to be well removed spatially from oxygen formation centres. We suggest the following mechanism for the formation of hydrogen, as the most probable one :

on the analogy of the well known reaction of heated sodium formate decomposing itself into forming sodium oxalate and hydrogen

the difference between (4) and (5) being that the latter being an ionic reaction gives rise to an ionic product, the oxalate ion, while in (4) the free radicals carbon dioxide in addition to hydrogen. Reaction (4) may be as slow or even slower than (3). Even in case it happens to be faster, the escape of all hydrogen may be rendered a bit difficult by the possibility of its oxidation by oxygen. The fact that hydrogen is one of the constituents of the anodic gases and may be the consequence of an overall effect is proof positive that (4) occurs at centres somewhat conveniently removed from those where oxygen atoms are produced. Reactions (3) and (4) occur only at high current densities when a large number of formate radicals is liberated per second on the anode and the probability of the various simultaneous reactions, fast and slow, manifesting themselves as a result of the saturation of the surface, becomes greater.